

Novel Object Recognition

(4 mice at a time/1 per chamber)

Each mouse will go through three consecutive days of behavior tasks - Locomotor, NOR Training, and NOR Trial.

DAY 1: LOCOMOTOR (Habituation)

Room under full lighting (top button), 20 min

1. Set up 4 double-wide opaque chambers to align under the 4 cameras.
2. Label mini whiteboards with **animal numbers, male/female, and channel/camera position.**
3. On the monitor: on the left side under Layout select **Standard (Default)** from the dropdown menu to display all 4 channels/cameras. Click the **video camera button** on the bottom of each of the 4 screens → select **Stop Manually** → OK to start recording on each channel. *(In the upper left corner of each screen the green video camera should turn to a blue circle.)*
4. Flash white boards with the animal number under each camera. Check on the monitor to make sure they are legible.
5. Remove whiteboards and place the mouse in the center of each chamber.
6. Close the black curtains. Leave the room, and start the timer for **20 minutes.**
7. After 20 minutes enter the room and click the video camera button on the monitor for each of the 4 channels to turn off the recording. *(In the upper left corner of each screen the blue circle should turn into a green video camera.)*

PICTURES

DAY 2: NOR Training

Room under dim lighting (next to last button), 10 min with same objects

1. Use double-wide opaque chambers and objects (blue square and grey circle) stored in the behavior room top cupboards.

Schwartz Lab
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2. Set up the 4 chambers to align under the 4 cameras and place the ruler inside.
3. Label mini whiteboards with the **animal number, male/female, and channel/camera position**. Place the mini whiteboard in the **center** of the respective chamber.
4. The animal sheet indicates which training object has been assigned to each mouse.

Based on the sheet, place the **two identical allocated objects** in the respective chamber on each side of the whiteboard. (*whiteboard ensures that distance between objects is equal for all mice, refer to pictures below*)

Each chamber should contain either two squares or two circles.

5. On the monitor: on the left side under Layout select **Standard (Default)** from the dropdown menu to display all 4 channels/cameras. Click the **video camera button** on the bottom of each of the 4 screens → select **Stop Manually** → OK to start recording on each channel. (In the upper left corner of each screen the green video camera should turn to a blue circle.)
6. Remove whiteboards and place the mouse in the center of each chamber.
7. Close the black curtains. Leave the room and start a timer for **10 minutes**.
8. After 10 minutes enter the room and click the video camera button on the monitor for each of the 4 channels to turn off the recording. (*In the upper left corner of each screen the blue circle should turn into a green video camera.*)
9. Clean everything with ethanol.

PICTURES

DAY 3: NOR Trial

Room under dim lighting (next to last button), 10 min with different objects

1. Use double-wide opaque chambers and objects (blue square and grey circle) stored in the behavior room top cupboards.
2. Set up the 4 chambers to align under the 4 cameras and place the ruler inside.
3. Label mini whiteboards with the **animal number, male/female, and channel/camera position**. Place the mini whiteboard in the **center** of the respective chamber.
4. The animal sheet 'TEST' column indicates which shape is the novel object. Notice that the sheet mentions an object on the left and a different object on the right. Each chamber should contain a blue square and a grey circle and their placement will depend on the sheet.

Follow the '**LEFT**' and '**RIGHT**' signs on the wall to place the **different objects** in the chamber on each side of the whiteboard. (*Do NOT refer to the set-up on the monitor*)

5. On the monitor: on the left side under Layout select **Standard (Default)** from the dropdown menu to display all 4 channels/cameras. Click the **video camera button** on the bottom of each of the 4 screens → select **Stop Manually** → OK to start recording on each channel. (In the upper left corner of each screen the green video camera should turn to a blue circle.)
6. Remove whiteboards and place the mouse in the center of each chamber.
7. Close the black curtains. Leave the room and start a timer for **10 minutes**.
8. After 10 minutes enter the room and click the video camera button on the monitor for each of the 4 channels to turn off the recording. (*In the upper left corner of each screen the blue circle should turn into a green video camera.*)
9. Clean everything with ethanol.